

Exploring the Feasibility of Nuclear Energy as a Low-Carbon Alternative

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ABSTRACT

The pursuit of low-carbon energy alternatives to fossil fuels has become increasingly pressing in order to meet the climate objectives outlined in the Paris Agreement. While renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar, are commendable options, their reliance on weather conditions can be a limiting factor. Considering new safety regulations and the growing demand for more reliable energy sources, the consideration of nuclear energy as a viable alternative has once again come to mind.

Though nuclear energy production generates highly dangerous waste, the volume produced is considerably smaller when compared to the emissions from fossil fuels, such as coal. The advent of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) further adds to the appeal of nuclear energy as a low-carbon alternative, as SMRs offer scalability, enabling the adjustment of energy production according to the needs at hand.

Given the implementation of international standards and a more responsible approach to the disposal of nuclear waste, it can be argued that nuclear energy remains a credible and low-carbon energy alternative for a sustainable energy future.

KEYWORDS

Nuclear Energy, Nuclear Fission, Small Modular Reactor's (SMR's), IAEA (International Atomic Energy Agency), IEA (International Energy Agency), U.S. NRC (United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission)

1 Introduction

Nuclear energy plays a significant role in supplying global energy, accounting for 5.0% of the total energy supply in 2019, according to the International Energy Agency (IEA).[1] Despite being not a renewable energy source, it is considered low-carbon due to its minimal CO₂-emissions during production. While the manufacturing and transportation of materials used in the construction of a nuclear power plant can contribute to higher CO₂-emissions, these are still relatively low when compared to fossil fuels like coal.

Nuclear energy also has an advantage over renewable energies such as wind and solar, which are heavily dependent on weather conditions and therefore limited in their deployment. Nuclear energy, with proper safety measures in place, can be built in a wider range of locations. The technology for reusing used fuel has been researched, but after multiple cycles the process becomes uneconomical. One major concern with nuclear energy is the potential for a catastrophic meltdown, as seen in events such as the Chernobyl disaster and the Fukushima disaster. In the first case barren land for hundreds of years and strong radiation was the result while in the latter case, the evacuation of 9 million people was necessary after a 9.0 magnitude earthquake and tsunami caused three reactors to overheat. However, the Japanese government started lifting evacuation orders after a few years in a 20 km radius around the plant after striving for radiation levels of around 0.23 micro-Sievert per hour (around 200 mrem per year. About double the standards according to the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission).[2]

The U.S. NRC states the following:

“The NRC limits the handling and use of radioactive materials such that no member of the public will receive a radiation dose of 2 millirems in any one hour from external radiation sources in an unrestricted area, or 100 millirems in a calendar year from both external and internal sources of radiation from each licensee.” [3]

Furthermore, in response to the needs of communities that are unable to utilize or store large amounts of energy produced by traditional nuclear power plants, researchers are exploring the potential of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs). As the name suggests, SMRs are smaller in size than traditional power plants and offer greater flexibility through their modular design, which allows multiple units to be combined to increase energy production as needed.

2 How nuclear energy is generated

Nuclear energy, as we know it today, is generated through a process called nuclear fission. During this process, the nucleus of an atom is split into smaller nuclei, releasing a tremendous amount of energy in the process. The most common example of

nuclear fission is the reaction that takes place when a neutron collides with an atom of uranium-235. The collision results in the splitting of the nucleus, producing two smaller nuclei and additional neutrons. These additional neutrons then collide with neighboring uranium-235 atoms, thereby triggering a chain reaction and releasing heat and radiation. This heat can be harnessed and converted into electricity, much like heat from fossil fuels is utilized to generate power. On the other hand, nuclear fusion, the process of combining two light atomic nuclei to form a heavier nucleus, remains in its research and development phase.[4]

3 Low-Carbon-Energy

The Paris Agreement is a **globally legally binding treaty** aimed at addressing the issue of climate change. It was adopted by 196 nations during the 21st Conference of Parties (COP 21) in Paris in 2015 and went into effect in 2016. The agreement aims to limit the rise of global temperatures to well below 2°C, with a target of keeping it at 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.[5]

To meet the commitments of the Paris Agreement, countries are encouraged to shift their investments towards low-carbon energy sources, known as "green" energy. Nuclear energy is considered a low-carbon energy source as it produces nearly zero carbon dioxide emissions during its operation. The carbon footprint of nuclear energy is measured over its entire lifecycle, including the manufacturing, transportation, and construction of the materials used in its production. Although it emits low levels of CO₂ directly, the construction process and transportation of materials for nuclear power plants still contributes to carbon emissions.

Next, follows a table from an IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) – Report from 2014 (page 1335), which summarizes several dozens of studies. All these numbers are in grams of carbon dioxide per kilowatt hour (gCO₂eq/kWh).

Options	Direct emissions	Infrastructure & supply chain emissions	Biogenic CO ₂ emissions and albedo effect	Methane emissions	Lifecycle emissions (incl. albedo effect)
	Min/Median/Max	Typical values			Min/Median/Max
Currently Commercially Available Technologies					
Coal—PC	670/750/870	9.6	0	47	740/820/910
Gas—Combined Cycle	350/370/490	1.6	0	91	410/490/650
Biomass—cofiring	n.a. ¹	–	–	–	620/740/890 ²
Biomass—dedicated	n.a. ¹	210	27	0	130/230/420 ²
Geothermal	0	45	0	0	6.0/38/79
Hydropower	0	19	0	88	1.0/24/2200
Nuclear	0	18	0	0	3.7/12/110
Concentrated Solar Power	0	29	0	0	8.8/27/63
Solar PV—rooftop	0	42	0	0	26/41/60
Solar PV—utility	0	66	0	0	18/48/180
Wind onshore	0	15	0	0	7.0/11/56
Wind offshore	0	17	0	0	8.0/12/35

Figure 1: The Minimum, Median and Maximum of emissions during a lifecycle from different energy resources [6]

One objective of the study is to measure the lifecycle emissions of different energy sources. The research results are presented in the form of Minimum, Median, and Maximum values. The aggregated minimum and median of the studies reveal low levels of CO₂-emissions, with the median being similar to wind power

and four times lower than solar power. However, the maximum reported by the IPCC is relatively high compared to other sources of energy. The maximum lifecycle emissions, though higher than wind and solar power, are still far less than coal and gas, which need to be phased out. There is considerable uncertainty in the lifecycle of a nuclear power plant that can affect the lifecycle emissions. Factors such as the method of uranium mining, the quality of resources, transportation costs, production costs of materials, and construction costs of the power plant can vary. A different scientific paper from Austria with a similar concept states a minimum of 1.4 gCO₂eq/kWh and a maximum of 288 gCO₂eq/kWh. The mean (not median) footprint was found to be 66 gCO₂eq/kWh, still below the fossil fuel values.[7]

Despite its favorable carbon footprint, the costs associated with creating and maintaining nuclear power plants are a cause for concern. A trend reflecting this can be observed in the data presented in the 2022 World Nuclear Energy Report.

Figure 2: Costs / MWh (megawatt hour) development from 2009 to 2021 [8]

The graph in the 2022 World Nuclear Energy Report displays the increasing costs associated with the creation and maintenance of nuclear power plants, as represented by the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) in USD per megawatt hour. Over the past year, there has been a substantial 36% rise in these costs, largely due to the rising operating and maintenance costs associated with aging nuclear power plants. If this trend persists, it may become increasingly economically unviable to invest in nuclear energy, rendering it a less desirable option for the generation of electricity.

4 Damages from nuclear energy

Nuclear energy and its associated radiation and nuclear waste are highly controversial topics. Many people fear the severe consequences a meltdown could have on the environment, as seen in the tragic disasters of Chernobyl and Fukushima. According to a report from the World Health Organization and United Nations, 50 people were directly attributed to radiation from the Chernobyl accident, with up to 4,000 estimated to die from its consequences.[9] Additionally, there are long-term health impacts

beyond just death tolls. The total ramifications of the Chernobyl disaster are difficult to estimate, as there are many variables to consider.

A comprehensive study by the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine and National Research Center for Radiation Medicine analyzed the health outcomes of 68,145 male clean-up workers of the 600,000 certified workers (referred to as "liquidators") who participated in the aftermath of the Chernobyl disaster. The study found that in 1988, 67.6% of the liquidators were in good health, but by 2012, only 5.5% could still be considered healthy. Over the course of 26 years, the number of individuals with disabilities skyrocketed from virtually zero to 250 cases per 1,000 people, with almost 90% of these cases being linked to exposure to radiation from the Chernobyl accident.[10] According to the L.A. Times the Soviet Union paid \$1.12 Billion Dollar to the victims of the Chernobyl accident.[11] It's estimated that Chernobyl will remain uninhabitable for at least one millennium, with some experts even speculating that it may be so for multiple millennia.

The aftermath of the Fukushima disaster has resulted in only a single officially recognized fatality to date. However, the long-term consequences of the disaster remain to be seen. Nevertheless, the area has been partially reoccupied by the government six years after the incident. The government has aimed to regain a level of radiation exposure of 0.23 micro-Sieverts per hour, which is about double the standards set by the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission.

Despite the severity of radiation, it can be easily measured with today's technology, making it a less enigmatic danger compared to the consequences of air pollution or other hazards. In fact, data shows that the death toll associated with nuclear energy has historically been lower than that of fossil fuels, though the impact of fossil fuels is often less visible. In 2013 researchers from the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies and Columbia University calculated the fatalities from coal, gas and nuclear and summarized their findings in units of deaths per terawatt hour.

electricity source	mean value (range)	unit ^b
coal	28.67 (7.15–114)	deaths/TWh
	77 (19.25–308)	deaths/TWh
	1045 (909–1182)	tCO ₂ -eq/GWh
natural gas	2.821 (0.7–11.2)	deaths/TWh
	602 (386–818)	tCO ₂ -eq/GWh
nuclear	0.074 (range not given)	deaths/TWh
	65 (10–130) ^d	tCO ₂ -eq/GWh

Figure 3: Deaths per terawatt hour from different electricity sources [12]

According to researchers from NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies and Columbia University, they discovered that the use of coal has caused significantly more deaths compared to nuclear energy. It is estimated that coal-related air pollution has claimed over 100 times the number of lives than nuclear energy.

“We calculate a mean value of 1.84 million human deaths prevented by world nuclear power production from 1971 to 2009, with an average of 76 000 prevented deaths/year from 2000 to 2009 (range 19 000–300 000)” [13]

5 Nuclear Waste Classification

The handling and disposal of nuclear waste is a highly debated topic in the discussion of nuclear energy. While radioactive waste classifications vary across the world, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) recognizes six classes of waste in their 2009 Safety Standards report.[14] While these classifications may not be universally accepted, they provide a basis for comparison. Efforts to unify these classifications have been underway, with documents like the "World Nuclear Waste Report, Focus Europe" published in November 2019 referencing the IAEA's classifications.[15]

The IAEA's six classes can be grouped into three categories for ease of comparison:

- lightly contaminated waste (contains the 4 classes of low-level-waste and below [14]), which can be disposed of in near-surface facilities.
- intermediate level waste, which requires disposal in deeper facilities of tens to hundreds of meters.
- high-level waste, which requires safe disposal in deep geological formations, typically hundreds of meters deep.

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) has reported that nearly 92% of radioactive waste is classified as low-level waste and will only emit radiation for a limited time, typically a few hundred years. This type of waste includes items such as tools, equipment, clothing used in nuclear production processes. About 7% of the radioactive waste is intermediate-level waste, which includes ion-exchange resins, chemical sludge, radioactive materials from reactor decommissioning, and sources used in radiation therapy. The remaining less than 1% is classified as high-level waste, which is largely composed of spent fuel rods that contained uranium during energy production.[16]

In Comparison to the World's Nuclear Association these numbers vary. They state a distribution of lightly contaminated waste, intermediate-level and high-level waste to be 90%, 7% and 3% respectively.[17]

The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) acknowledges that it only has records for about 95% of the world's nuclear waste, due to limitations in data acquisition and varying

classifications used by different countries. However, despite these inaccuracies in classification, the total volume of nuclear waste is considered to be accurate.[16] High-level waste, which constitutes just 3% of the total volume, holds 95% of the radioactivity in the entire waste generated by the nuclear industry.[18]

High-level radioactive waste is primarily composed of Strontium-90 and Cesium-137, which have half-lives of approximately thirty years. However, the biggest concern is the presence of Plutonium-239, which has a half-life of 24,000 years, making it a hazard for approximately 100,000 years. Ten years after removal from a reactor, the surface dose rate of a typical spent fuel assembly is reported to surpass 10,000 rem/hour, which is significantly higher than the fatal dose of 500 rem if consumed in one instance, according to the U.S. NRC.[19]

As of the end of 2016, the IAEA reports that a global total of 390,000 metric tons of spent nuclear waste, or high-level waste, had been produced. This is the cumulative result of all spent fuel discharged from nuclear power plants since the first one was established in 1954.[16] The amount increases each year by more than 10,000 tons.[20]

A single standard nuclear plant has the capacity to produce 44 million kilowatt hours of energy with just 1 ton of natural uranium. To generate this same amount of energy through fossil fuels, the burning of more than 20,000 tons of coal would be required. The ash produced by just one coal plant in one year alone surpasses the entire amount of high-level nuclear waste produced globally to date.[21], [22]

5.1 Nuclear Waste Storage

Once energy production is complete, the depleted fuel rods are removed from the reactor core. To begin with, they are stored in a pool of water adjacent to the reactor for several years to allow for the cooling down of the rods and the decay of some of the nucleotides with short half-lives. The issue of how to proceed from this point remains unresolved. The most widely adopted solution is to transfer the rods to dry cask storage systems, often located directly at the power plant site. These systems serve as temporary storage and consist of steel canisters encased in concrete, filled with an inert gas such as helium or nitrogen. [23] Each weigh more than 100 tons. These encased rods still emit roughly 0.01 milli-Sievert per hour. If standing next to them for 100 hours, according to the U.S.NRC, the annual dose of background radiation (1 milli-Sievert = 100mrem) is met. [3] In Comparison an average American has a yearly dose of around 620 mrem from all sources combined.

According to the IAEA report, as of 2016, of the 390,000 metric tons of spent nuclear fuel produced globally, 47% (183,000 tons) were stored in cooling pools for wet storage, 21% (80,000 tons) were stored in concrete and steel canisters for dry storage, and the remaining 32% had been reprocessed.[24] This high-level waste has to be transported in special containers and train carriages. In

1984 a train was intentionally crashed into one of those train carriages, carrying only dummy container, with a speed of over 100 mph. A force greater than 8 million pounds was subjected on to the carriages, but the force caused only light deformations, while the train got destroyed.[25]

To safely contain high-level radioactive waste, deep geological repositories are the widely agreed upon solution. Finland is leading the way in this regard, with the construction of the world's first such repository, the "Onkalo" nuclear fuel repository. Situated near a nuclear power plant on the west coast of Finland, this repository will be buried 420 meters deep and will consist of thousands of corrosion-resistant copper canisters. These canisters will be sealed with bentonite, a water-absorbing clay, and the tunnels will be filled with more bentonite and sealed with concrete, ensuring the safe containment of this hazardous waste for generations to come.[26]

Additionally, there are teams of several experts such as engineers, nuclear physicists, behavioral scientists, philosophers and so on to warn people across those 100,000 years with signs and other ideas.

6 Foresight

There are emerging technologies such as Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) that offer a more flexible and efficient solution for nuclear power generation. SMRs are essentially smaller reactors that can be combined to form larger systems, making it easier to scale up or down as needed. In terms of size, SMRs typically measure 4.6 meters in diameter and 23.3 meters in height, taking up significantly less space compared to traditional large-scale nuclear reactors.[27]

At present, every nuclear power plant requires its own individual licensing. However, the use of Small Modular Reactors (SMR's) has the potential to streamline the licensing process by allowing for a standardized patent and mass production. This could lead to a reduction in cost and an increase in security due to the implementation of standard safety protocols in mass production. However, there are concerns that cost-saving measures may result in shortcuts being taken in the quality of materials used.

According to a study conducted by Stanford University, the utilization of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) compared to conventional nuclear power plants may result in an increase in the volume of nuclear waste generated. Specifically, the analysis found that the energy-equivalent volumes of spent nuclear fuel (SNF), which refers to High-level waste in this context, low- and intermediate-level waste (LILW) of long-lived and short-lived nature, could increase by up to 5.5, 30, and 35 times, respectively.[28]

7 Conclusion

As a non-supporter of nuclear energy, this newfound information brings a new light into things. Nuclear energy is in many cases a good low-carbon alternative to fossil fuels. Furthermore, nuclear energy production has little to no downtime, in contrary to other low-carbon energies like solar or wind energy which depend on the weather. In recent years and through the negative perception of the public, nuclear safety and waste regulations are becoming more and more advanced. This paths the way for a more responsible caretaking of nuclear waste. Contrary to common believe, the nuclear power production is not as deadly in comparison to other low-carbon alternatives. To sum it up, with international safety and waste regulation standards, nuclear energy can be a reliable low-carbon alternative to further reduce CO₂-emissions.

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